

Appendix

**INTERVIEW GUIDE
AND
INTERVIEW DATA RESULTS**
(English)

**PANDUAN WAWANCARA
DAN
HASIL DATA WAWANCARA**
(Indonesian)

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Perceived Physical Fitness Improvements Through Adapted Sports Programming for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities: A Multi-Stakeholder Qualitative Analysis

Type	Semi-structured, open-ended
Duration	±30–50 minutes
Technique	In-depth Interview
Recording	Audio (with informed consent)
Location	School / community / home (as agreed)
Focus	Physical fitness gains, adapted programming, assessment practices

NOTES FOR INTERVIEWER

- Use simple and empathetic language throughout the interview.
- Allow sufficient time for the respondent to think and respond.
- Use neutral probing: 'Could you tell me more?', 'What do you mean by that?', 'How did you feel at that moment?'
- Avoid leading or suggestive questions.
- Focus questions on physical fitness changes, program adaptations used, and how improvement is observed.

PART I — INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR TEACHERS / COACHES

1 Opening

- How long have you been involved in the sports program?
- What is your primary role in the sports program (e.g., PE teacher, homeroom teacher, coach, coordinator)?

2 Observable Physical Improvements

Main Questions:

1. Have you observed improvements in students' physical capabilities (e.g., stamina, strength, motor coordination) since joining the sports program?
2. Can you describe specific examples of physical changes you have noticed in individual students?
3. How do physically active students differ from less active students in terms of physical condition and performance?

Probing:

- ▶ *Can you describe a student whose physical ability changed significantly after joining the program?*
- ▶ *Have students shown improvement in fundamental motor skills such as balance, running, or coordination?*
- ▶ *Are there differences in physical improvement between students who attend regularly and those who attend less consistently?*
- ▶ *Have you noticed any improvements in students' focus or stamina during activities?*

3 Individualized Program Adaptation

Main Questions:

1. What types of adaptations do you provide to accommodate students' individual needs and disability levels?
2. How are game rules or training methods modified to facilitate students' participation?
3. How do you select appropriate sports for students based on their individual abilities and disability type?

Probing:

- ▶ *What equipment modifications do you use (e.g., ball size, texture, weight) to match students' physical capacities?*
- ▶ *Are there graduated steps you use when introducing new physical tasks — for example, starting with simpler versions and building up?*
- ▶ *How do you differentiate training for students with mild versus severe intellectual disability?*
- ▶ *Do you draw on frameworks such as Special Olympics Indonesia (SOINA) for sport selection and rule modification?*
- ▶ *How do you match sport selection to each student's strengths and competition requirements?*

4 Assessment and Monitoring Practices**Main Questions:**

1. How do you assess or monitor students' physical fitness improvements over time?
2. Do you use formal assessment tools, or is monitoring primarily observational? Please describe.
3. How do competition results or performance outcomes inform your understanding of students' fitness progress?

Probing:

- ▶ *What specific physical indicators do you look for when observing students during training (e.g., posture, endurance, movement quality)?*
- ▶ *Do you share your observations with parents? How?*
- ▶ *How do you track progress for students who are not competing in formal competitions?*
- ▶ *Has a student's performance in competition ever surprised you based on their training progress?*

5 Challenges & Program Sustainability**Main Questions:**

1. What are the main challenges in implementing the adapted sports program?
2. Are facilities and resources sufficient to support the physical training adaptations you described?
3. Do you believe the sports program will continue? What supports its sustainability?

PART II — INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR PARENTS

1 Opening (Rapport Building)

- Could you tell me a little about your child? (age, type of disability, daily activities)
- How long has your child been participating in the sports program?

2 Observable Physical Improvements at Home

Main Questions:

1. Have you noticed changes in your child's physical condition since joining the sports program?
2. What about their stamina, strength, or movement coordination?
3. Has your child's general health changed — for example, getting sick less often?

Probing:

- ▶ *Is your child more physically active at home than before joining the program?*
- ▶ *Have you noticed changes in your child's sleep quality or energy levels?*
- ▶ *Has there been an increase in independence in daily physical tasks (e.g., personal care, household chores)?*
- ▶ *Can you describe a specific moment when you noticed a physical change in your child?*

3 Awareness of Program Adaptations

Main Questions:

1. Are you aware of any special adaptations made by teachers or coaches to suit your child's needs?
2. Has your child mentioned specific sports or activities they particularly enjoy or find accessible?

Probing:

- ▶ *Has your child been assigned to a sport that seems particularly well-matched to their abilities?*
- ▶ *Has any teacher or coach explained to you how they adjust training to fit your child's condition?*

4 Home-Based Monitoring and Support

Main Questions:

1. How do you monitor or notice your child's physical progress at home?
2. Have teachers or coaches communicated with you about your child's physical improvement?
3. What support does the school or community provide for your child's physical development?

Probing:

- ▶ *Have there been any challenges in supporting your child's sports participation at home?*
- ▶ *Is there any follow-up exercise or physical activity your child does at home?*

5 Reflection & Recommendations

Main Questions:

1. In your view, what is the greatest physical benefit of this program for your child?
2. What improvements in the program would further support your child's physical development?
3. Would you recommend this program to other parents of children with similar needs? Why?

PEDOMAN WAWANCARA

Perceived Physical Fitness Improvements Through Adapted Sports Programming for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities: A Multi-Stakeholder Qualitative Analysis

Jenis	Wawancara Semi-terstruktur, terbuka
Durasi	±30–50 menit
Teknik	In-depth Interview
Rekaman	Audio (dengan informed consent)
Lokasi	Sekolah / komunitas / rumah (sesuai kesepakatan)
Fokus	Peningkatan kebugaran fisik, adaptasi program, dan praktik penilaian

CATATAN UNTUK PEWAWANCARA

- Gunakan bahasa yang sederhana dan empatik.
- Berikan waktu cukup bagi responden untuk berpikir dan merespons.
- Gunakan probing netral: 'Bisa diceritakan lebih lanjut?', 'Apa maksudnya?', 'Bagaimana perasaan Anda saat itu?'
- Hindari pertanyaan yang bersifat sugestif atau mengarahkan.
- Fokuskan pertanyaan pada perubahan kebugaran fisik, adaptasi yang digunakan dalam program, dan cara kemajuan diamati.

BAGIAN I — PEDOMAN WAWANCARA GURU / PELATIH

1 Pembuka

- Sudah berapa lama Bapak/Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga ini?
- Apa peran utama Bapak/Ibu dalam program olahraga (misalnya guru penjaskes, wali kelas, pelatih, koordinator)?

2 Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apakah Bapak/Ibu mengamati peningkatan kemampuan fisik siswa (misalnya stamina, kekuatan, koordinasi gerak) setelah mengikuti program olahraga?
2. Bisakah Bapak/Ibu menggambarkan contoh perubahan fisik spesifik yang terlihat pada siswa tertentu?
3. Bagaimana perbedaan kondisi fisik dan performa antara siswa yang aktif berolahraga dan yang kurang aktif?

Probing:

- ▶ *Bisakah Bapak/Ibu menceritakan siswa yang kemampuan fisiknya berubah signifikan setelah mengikuti program?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada peningkatan pada kemampuan motorik dasar seperti keseimbangan, berlari, atau koordinasi gerak?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada perbedaan peningkatan fisik antara siswa yang rutin hadir dan yang kurang konsisten?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada peningkatan fokus atau stamina siswa selama kegiatan berlangsung?*

3 Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Jenis adaptasi apa yang Bapak/Ibu berikan untuk mengakomodasi kebutuhan dan tingkat disabilitas siswa secara individual?
2. Bagaimana aturan permainan atau metode latihan dimodifikasi untuk memfasilitasi partisipasi siswa?
3. Bagaimana Bapak/Ibu memilih cabang olahraga yang sesuai berdasarkan kemampuan dan jenis ketunaan masing-masing siswa?

Probing:

- ▶ *Modifikasi peralatan apa yang digunakan (misalnya ukuran bola, tekstur, berat) untuk menyesuaikan kapasitas fisik siswa?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada tahapan bertahap dalam memperkenalkan tugas fisik baru — misalnya dimulai dari versi yang lebih sederhana lalu ditingkatkan?*
- ▶ *Bagaimana Bapak/Ibu membedakan latihan untuk siswa tunagrahita ringan dan berat?*
- ▶ *Apakah Bapak/Ibu mengacu pada kerangka seperti SOINA dalam pemilihan olahraga dan modifikasi aturan?*
- ▶ *Bagaimana pencocokan cabang olahraga dengan kekuatan dan kebutuhan kompetisi masing-masing siswa?*

4 Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Bagaimana Bapak/Ibu menilai atau memantau peningkatan kebugaran fisik siswa dari waktu ke waktu?
2. Apakah digunakan instrumen penilaian formal, atau pemantauan dilakukan secara observasional? Mohon dijelaskan.
3. Bagaimana hasil kompetisi atau performa siswa membantu Bapak/Ibu memahami kemajuan kebugaran mereka?

Probing:

- ▶ *Indikator fisik spesifik apa yang Bapak/Ibu amati saat melihat siswa berlatih (misalnya postur, daya tahan, kualitas gerak)?*
- ▶ *Apakah hasil pengamatan disampaikan kepada orang tua? Bagaimana caranya?*
- ▶ *Bagaimana Bapak/Ibu memantau kemajuan siswa yang tidak mengikuti kompetisi formal?*
- ▶ *Apakah pernah ada siswa yang performanya di kompetisi mengejutkan Bapak/Ibu berdasarkan kemajuan latihannya?*

5 Tantangan dan Keberlanjutan Program

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apa tantangan utama dalam menjalankan program olahraga adaptif ini?
2. Apakah fasilitas dan sumber daya sudah memadai untuk mendukung adaptasi latihan fisik yang Bapak/Ibu jelaskan?
3. Apakah Bapak/Ibu yakin program olahraga akan terus berlanjut? Apa yang mendukung keberlanjutannya?

BAGIAN II — PEDOMAN WAWANCARA ORANG TUA

1 Pembuka (Rapport Building)

- Bisa diceritakan sedikit tentang anak Bapak/Ibu? (usia, jenis disabilitas, aktivitas sehari-hari)
- Sudah berapa lama anak mengikuti program olahraga?

2 Peningkatan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati di Rumah

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apakah Bapak/Ibu melihat perubahan pada kondisi fisik anak setelah mengikuti program olahraga?
2. Bagaimana dengan daya tahan tubuh, kekuatan, atau koordinasi gerakannya?
3. Apakah kesehatan anak secara umum berubah — misalnya lebih jarang sakit?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah anak lebih aktif bergerak di rumah dibanding sebelum mengikuti program?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada perubahan pada kualitas tidur atau tingkat energi anak?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada peningkatan kemandirian dalam aktivitas fisik sehari-hari (misalnya merawat diri, membantu di rumah)?*
- ▶ *Bisakah Bapak/Ibu menceritakan momen tertentu ketika Anda pertama kali menyadari perubahan fisik pada anak?*

3 Kesadaran terhadap Adaptasi Program

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apakah Bapak/Ibu mengetahui adanya adaptasi khusus yang diberikan guru atau pelatih untuk kebutuhan anak?
2. Apakah anak pernah menyebutkan cabang olahraga atau aktivitas tertentu yang ia sukai atau rasa mudah diikuti?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah anak ditempatkan dalam cabang olahraga yang tampaknya sesuai dengan kemampuannya?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada guru atau pelatih yang pernah menjelaskan kepada Bapak/Ibu bagaimana latihan disesuaikan dengan kondisi anak?*

4 Pemantauan dan Dukungan di Rumah

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Bagaimana Bapak/Ibu memantau atau menyadari kemajuan fisik anak di rumah?
2. Apakah ada komunikasi dari guru atau pelatih mengenai peningkatan fisik anak?
3. Dukungan apa yang diberikan sekolah atau komunitas untuk perkembangan fisik anak?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah ada hambatan dalam mendukung partisipasi olahraga anak di rumah?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada latihan fisik atau aktivitas olahraga tambahan yang dilakukan anak di rumah?*

5 Refleksi & Rekomendasi

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Menurut Bapak/Ibu, apa manfaat fisik terbesar dari program ini bagi anak?
2. Perbaikan apa dalam program yang menurut Bapak/Ibu akan semakin mendukung perkembangan fisik anak?
3. Apakah Bapak/Ibu merekomendasikan program ini kepada orang tua lain dengan anak berkebutuhan serupa? Mengapa?

INTERVIEW DATA RESULTS

SECTION A: TEACHER INTERVIEWS

TEACHER T1 — DHEA PUTRI DEFIYANTI

PE Teacher | 10 years experience | SLB 1 Negeri Padang

Q1: How long have you been involved?

I started working at SLB in 2014. Previously at SLB 2 Lubuk Buaya, now at SLB 1 Negeri Padang. In total, approximately 10 years.

Q2: What is your main role?

My role is as physical education teacher, supervisor, and coach. We select students capable of competing, first looking at physical condition and health, then how well they respond to instructions.

Q3: Have you observed improvements in students' physical capabilities?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes. For example, Fajri — he was lazy at first. With training programs and intensive motivation, he eventually won first place in the long jump at WNP. Progress is evident when enthusiasm is planted strongly.

Q4: Can you describe specific physical changes in individual students?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Fajri showed dramatic improvement in physical fitness and coordination. After structured training, he not only won the long jump but also gained the confidence to participate in flag ceremonies — something he had never done before.

Q5: What types of adaptations do you provide?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Grouping is essential. A mild tunagrahita (C) student is not placed in the same group as a severe (C1) student because the gap is very large. C1 students can only participate in certain sports like bocce, which requires only minimal hand-eye coordination.

Q6: Are game rules modified?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Bocce is specifically designed for children with Down Syndrome — part of the Paralympics and modified by SOINA (Special Olympics Indonesia). It is a small-ball sport similar to modified bowling.

Q7: How do you assess physical fitness improvements?

[Theme: Assessment and Monitoring Practices]

Primarily through observation during activities. I also use competition results as benchmarks. Parent-reported changes at home — such as increased energy, improved stamina, and greater independence — also inform my understanding of each student's progress.

Q8: Main challenges?

The biggest challenge is with autistic students. I don't have a special education background (PLB), so when they have tantrums I am at a loss.

Q9: Are facilities sufficient?

Very much so. We have a budget every semester and the school has complete facilities: fashion, culinary arts, beauty, music with a full band.

Q10: Will the program continue?

Very confident. With PERNAS, SOINA, and Special Olympics, talented students will keep advancing. There are 3 competitions per year at various levels — city, provincial, and national.

TEACHER T2 — FITRIANI

Mentor / Coach | 26 years experience

Q1: How long have you been involved?

I have been a teacher since 2000 — almost 26 years.

Q2: Have you observed physical improvements?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes. Students who actively engage in Thursday morning physical exercises show notable improvement in their fitness. Regular physical activity builds their stamina and strength.

Q3: What adaptations are provided?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

At our school, we use regular sports equipment. Modification is mainly applied for tunarungu students. For tunagrahita students, training intensity and rules are adjusted.

Q4: Main challenges?

The main challenge is the technical knowledge gap. As teachers with general education backgrounds, we need to constantly learn the correct techniques for each sport.

Q5: Will the program continue?

Definitely, because it is part of the formal school curriculum. There are structured weekly sports activities every Thursday.

TEACHER T3 — GEMI SAPUTRI

Classroom Teacher, Grade 8 SMPLB | 17 years experience

Q1: Have you observed physical improvements?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes. Some students used to trip and fall easily. After physical training, they become stronger, more stable, and can run with confidence. There is significant improvement — students who initially fell easily have become stronger and rarely fall now.

Q2: How do you measure physical improvement?

[Theme: Assessment and Monitoring Practices]

Primarily through observation. We watch their daily movement, posture, and physical endurance over time. Competition performance also serves as a key benchmark.

Q3: What forms of adaptation are provided?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

For students with weak physical fitness, we consult with the PE teacher to tailor activities. Rule modifications are essential and proven effective in facilitating student participation.

Q4: Are game rules modified?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Yes, rules must be modified. Modification in sports at SLB is not only acceptable — it is essential and proven effective in facilitating students' participation.

TEACHER T4 — GILANG DWI NANDA

Arts Teacher / SOINA Coordinator | 12 years experience

Q1: Have you observed physical improvements?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes. Previously, some students who appeared sleepy or unfocused were actually just physically unfit. After regular sports, endurance and stamina improved. There are clear improvements in stamina, focus, concentration, and physical strength among students who were previously characterized as lethargic or physically unfit.

Q2: Can you describe a specific example?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Audia showed remarkable physical improvement through regular swimming therapy. Swimming reduced her health risks significantly. Khalid transferred from a regular school where he was bullied. When swimming was identified as his strength, he competed and won — his physical confidence transformed completely.

Q3: What adaptations are provided?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Curriculum adaptations are standard practice. For tunarungu students, visual cues replace verbal signals. For tunagrahita students, content is simplified. For wheelchair users, running is modified to wheelchair racing. Sport selection is based on each student's individual ability.

Q4: How do you assess physical improvement?

[Theme: Assessment and Monitoring Practices]

Through observing student enthusiasm and capability during activities. We don't use formal observation sheets — the assessment is qualitative and personalized. Competition performance provides secondary benchmarks.

TEACHER T5 — LILIANA SARI

Homeroom Teacher, SDLB | 16 years experience

Q1: Have you observed physical improvements?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Even small activities yield big results. Asking a child to walk on top of lined-up chairs (20 cm high) to train balance seems trivial to others, but to our students it is a significant challenge. After 4–5 sessions, a child who was terrified gradually becomes confident.

Q2: How do you measure physical improvement?

[Theme: Assessment and Monitoring Practices]

Physical improvements are assessed through visual observation of student enthusiasm and capability during activities. We don't use formal observation sheets — the assessment is qualitative and personalized, shared with parents.

Q3: What forms of adaptation are used?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Students who can't do a balance board yet go through simpler steps: walking on lines first, then on tiles, then on the board. For balls: small balls before large ones. Each step is scaffolded based on the child's current ability.

Q4: Are game rules modified?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Yes. In one class there might be students from Grade 2 through Grade 4 with varying cognitive levels. Games teach life skills simultaneously — queuing, following rules, teamwork.

TEACHER T6 — RINI AGUSTA

Vice Principal for Curriculum | 37 years experience

Q1: Have you observed physical improvements?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes. The physical differences, agility, and technique — for example in holding a racket or kicking a ball — are clearly visible between students who regularly exercise and those who don't. For bocce players, improvement is visible in their focus and precision of rolling the ball.

Q2: What adaptations are provided?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

Training is adapted to each student's ability level. Everything — from tools to training intensity — is tailored to the student's physical and cognitive capacity.

Q3: How do you monitor physical progress?

[Theme: Assessment and Monitoring Practices]

Primarily through observational assessment during weekly joint exercise sessions (every Thursday) and during extracurricular training. Competition performance also provides benchmarks. Changes visible to parents at home triangulate our school-based observations.

TEACHER T7 — ROSMADAWATI

Coach | 2 years at this school

Q1: Have you observed physical improvements?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — students who regularly engage in sports appear more physically fit. Students appear more upright, stronger, and more capable over time.

Q2: What adaptations are used?

[Theme: Individualized Program Adaptation]

We adjust the equipment using balls that are not too hard, textured balls for fine motor training, or smaller balls to develop catching skills. The training is adapted to each student's individual capability.

Q3: How do you measure physical improvement?

[Theme: Assessment and Monitoring Practices]

By observing strength, posture, and resilience — students appear more upright, stronger, and more capable over time. When training and tools are matched to a student's needs, the impact is clear and meaningful.

SECTION B: PARENT INTERVIEWS

PARENT P1 — GUSLINA

Guardian of twins Zikra and Zikri (16 years old, tunagrahita) | 7 years in program

Q1: Have you noticed changes in your children's physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — visible physical development and improved strength. They are hardy — indifferent to rain or sun. There is good physical development, improved endurance — they rarely get sick — and strong physical strength. Their busy activities make them sleep well earlier and wake up refreshed.

Q2: Have they become more independent?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — after sports days, they wash their own sports clothes without being told.

Q3: Are you aware of any adaptations made?

[Theme: Awareness of Program Adaptations]

The teachers are focused and dedicated. The children are assigned activities that suit their level.

PARENT P2 — HERLINA DEWIFERI

Mother of Fajri (16 years old, tunagrahita) | Badminton competitor

Q1: Have you noticed changes in Fajri's physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — he rarely gets sick, even though he is often out in the sun or rain. His son rarely gets sick, even in hot weather or rain, thanks to his high physical activity. His physical endurance is notably strong.

Q2: Has sport made him more independent?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes. When there's no food at home, he cooks his own noodles. He is self-sufficient in daily tasks.

PARENT P3 — IKHSAN ENDRIZUL

Father of 17-year-old student (swimmer/runner)

Q1: Have you noticed changes in your son's physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — moderately improved. He is rarely sick. He has become more independent.

Q2: Is he more active at home?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

His activity level at home remains about the same.

PARENT P4 — JUSNIWATI

Mother of 15–16-year-old student (tunagrahita)

Q1: Have you noticed changes in your child's physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — physically she seems stronger. She does get sick occasionally, but it is not severe.

Q2: Are you aware of adaptations in the program?

[Theme: Awareness of Program Adaptations]

I am not certain of the full scope — I am often at work when she is home.

PARENT P5 — ELI YARNI

Mother of Rio (15 years old, tunagrahita) | 7 years in program

Q1: Have you noticed changes in Rio's physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — you can see that he has more energy. He is also healthier — rarely sick since doing regular sports.

Q2: Main challenges?

He lacks focus without a companion. He needs a dedicated coach or teacher who is consistently present.

PARENT P6 — MUNIARTI

Mother of Khalid (18 years old) | Swimmer

Q1: Have you noticed changes in his physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

His physical endurance has improved — he is more resilient. He is somewhat more active at home.

PARENT P7 — RENI SURYANI

Mother of Imam (teenager, tunagrahita) | Multiple competition winner

Q1: Have you noticed changes in Imam's physical condition?

[Theme: Observable Physical Improvements]

Yes — his physical endurance has improved since being active in sports.

LAMPIRAN — DATA HASIL WAWANCARA

BAGIAN A: WAWANCARA GURU

GURU T1 — DHEA PUTRI DEFIYANTI

Guru Penjaskes | 10 tahun pengalaman | SLB 1 Negeri Padang

P1: Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat?

Saya mulai bekerja di SLB dari tahun 2014. Sebelumnya di SLB 2 Lubuk Buaya, sekarang di SLB 1 Negeri Padang. Kurang lebih sudah 10 tahun.

P2: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik siswa setelah mengikuti program?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ada. Contohnya Fajri – awalnya malas. Dengan program latihan dan motivasi intens, akhirnya ia juara satu lompat jauh di WNP. Ada perubahan nyata, terutama jika semangat ditanamkan dengan kuat.

P3: Bisakah Ibu menggambarkan contoh spesifik?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Fajri menunjukkan peningkatan luar biasa dalam kebugaran fisik dan koordinasi. Setelah latihan terstruktur, ia tidak hanya memenangkan lompat jauh tetapi juga mendapat kepercayaan diri untuk mengikuti upacara bendera.

P4: Jenis adaptasi apa yang diberikan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Pengelompokan sangat penting. Siswa tunagrahita C biasa tidak dicampur dengan C1 karena kemampuannya sangat berbeda. Siswa C1 hanya mengikuti olahraga tertentu seperti bocce yang hanya membutuhkan koordinasi tangan ringan.

P5: Apakah aturan permainan dimodifikasi?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Bocce memang sudah dirancang khusus untuk anak Down Syndrome — ada di Paralimpik dan telah dimodifikasi oleh SOINA (Special Olympics Indonesia).

P6: Bagaimana Ibu menilai atau memantau peningkatan kebugaran fisik?

[Tema: Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan]

Terutama melalui observasi selama kegiatan. Hasil kompetisi juga menjadi tolok ukur. Perubahan yang dilaporkan orang tua di rumah — seperti peningkatan energi, stamina, dan kemandirian sehari-hari — juga memperkaya pemahaman saya.

GURU T2 — FITRIANI

Pembimbing / Pelatih | 26 tahun pengalaman

P1: Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat?

Saya sudah mengajar sejak tahun 2000, hampir 26 tahun.

P2: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti program?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya. Siswa yang aktif mengikuti senam pagi hari Kamis menunjukkan peningkatan kebugaran yang signifikan. Aktivitas fisik rutin membangun stamina dan kekuatan mereka.

P3: Adaptasi apa yang diberikan dalam latihan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Di sekolah kami peralatan yang digunakan masih standar. Modifikasi lebih banyak diterapkan untuk siswa tunarungu. Untuk siswa tunagrahita, intensitas latihan dan aturan disesuaikan.

GURU T3 — GEMI SAPUTRI

Wali Kelas 8 SMPLB Tunagrahita | 17 tahun pengalaman

P1: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti olahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya. Siswa tunagrahita bisa mengalami tantangan fisik – beberapa dulu sering jatuh meski berjalan di tempat datar. Setelah latihan fisik rutin, mereka menjadi lebih kuat, lebih stabil, dan akhirnya bisa berlari dengan percaya diri.

P2: Bagaimana cara mengukur peningkatan fisik?

[Tema: Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan]

Terutama melalui observasi. Kami memperhatikan pergerakan, postur, dan daya tahan fisik dari waktu ke waktu. Hasil kompetisi juga menjadi tolok ukur utama.

P3: Bentuk penyesuaian apa yang diberikan saat latihan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Untuk siswa dengan kebugaran fisik lemah, kami berkonsultasi dengan guru olahraga untuk menyesuaikan kegiatan. Modifikasi aturan terbukti efektif dalam memfasilitasi partisipasi siswa.

GURU T4 — GILANG DWI NANDA

Guru Seni Budaya / Koordinator SOINA | 12 tahun pengalaman

P1: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah berpartisipasi dalam olahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya. Sebelumnya, beberapa siswa yang tampak mengantuk atau kurang fokus ternyata hanya karena kebugaran fisik yang rendah. Ada peningkatan yang jelas dalam stamina, fokus, konsentrasi, dan kekuatan fisik pada siswa yang sebelumnya dikategorikan malas atau kurang bugar.

P2: Bisakah Bapak memberikan contoh spesifik?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Audia menunjukkan peningkatan fisik luar biasa melalui terapi renang rutin. Khalid, yang pindah dari sekolah reguler karena di-bully, ketika renang diidentifikasi sebagai kekuatannya dan ia diikuti lomba, ternyata menang — kepercayaan dirinya berubah total.

P3: Adaptasi apa yang diberikan saat latihan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Adaptasi kurikulum adalah standar bagi siswa berkebutuhan khusus. Untuk tunarungu, isyarat visual menggantikan sinyal verbal. Untuk tunagrahita, materi disederhanakan. Untuk pengguna kursi roda, kegiatan berlari dimodifikasi menjadi balap kursi roda.

P4: Bagaimana Bapak menilai peningkatan fisik?

[Tema: Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan]

Melalui observasi terhadap antusiasme dan kemampuan siswa selama kegiatan. Kami tidak menggunakan lembar observasi formal — penilaiannya kualitatif dan personal. Hasil kompetisi menjadi tolok ukur sekunder.

GURU T5 — LILIANA SARI

Wali Kelas SDLB | 16 tahun pengalaman

P1: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti olahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Bahkan aktivitas kecil sekalipun memberikan hasil yang besar. Meminta anak berjalan di atas kursi yang disusun berjejer untuk melatih keseimbangan tampak sepele bagi orang lain, tapi bagi siswa kita adalah tantangan signifikan. Setelah 4–5 kali pertemuan, anak yang tadinya sangat takut perlahan menjadi percaya diri.

P2: Bagaimana cara mengukur peningkatan fisik?

[Tema: Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan]

Peningkatan fisik dinilai melalui observasi visual terhadap antusiasme dan kemampuan siswa selama kegiatan. Tidak menggunakan lembar observasi formal — penilaiannya kualitatif dan personal, disampaikan kepada orang tua.

P3: Bentuk adaptasi apa yang digunakan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Siswa yang belum bisa menggunakan papan titian melewati tahapan lebih sederhana: berjalan di garis dulu, kemudian di atas ubin, baru ke papan. Untuk bola: bola kecil terlebih dahulu sebelum bola besar. Setiap langkah di-scaffold berdasarkan kemampuan anak saat ini.

GURU T6 — RINI AGUSTA

Wakasek Bidang Kurikulum | 37 tahun pengalaman

P1: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik siswa?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya. Kita bisa melihat perbedaan fisik yang jelas antara siswa yang rutin berolahraga dengan yang tidak. Perbedaan fisik, kelincahan, dan teknik — misalnya dalam memegang raket atau menendang bola — terlihat jelas.

P2: Adaptasi apa yang diberikan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Latihan disesuaikan dengan tingkat kemampuan setiap siswa. Semuanya — dari alat hingga intensitas latihan — disesuaikan dengan kapasitas fisik dan kognitif siswa.

P3: Bagaimana pemantauan kemajuan fisik dilakukan?

[Tema: Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan]

Terutama melalui penilaian observasional selama sesi senam bersama mingguan (setiap Kamis) dan latihan ekstrakurikuler. Hasil kompetisi juga menjadi tolok ukur. Perubahan yang terlihat orang tua di rumah memperkuat observasi kami di sekolah.

GURU T7 — ROSMADAWATI

Pelatih | 2 tahun di sekolah ini

P1: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti olahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — siswa yang rutin berolahraga tampak lebih bugar secara fisik. Siswa tampak lebih tegak, lebih kuat, dan lebih mampu dari waktu ke waktu.

P2: Adaptasi apa yang digunakan dalam latihan?

[Tema: Adaptasi Program yang Disesuaikan dengan Individu]

Kami menyesuaikan peralatan menggunakan bola yang tidak terlalu keras, bola bertekstur untuk latihan motorik halus, atau bola lebih kecil untuk mengembangkan kemampuan menangkap. Latihan diadaptasi sesuai kemampuan individual siswa.

P3: Bagaimana cara mengukur peningkatan fisik?

[Tema: Praktik Penilaian dan Pemantauan]

Dengan mengamati kekuatan, postur, dan ketahanan — siswa tampak lebih tegak, lebih kuat, dan lebih mampu dari waktu ke waktu. Ketika latihan dan alat disesuaikan dengan kebutuhan siswa, dampaknya jelas dan bermakna.

BAGIAN B: WAWANCARA ORANG TUA

ORANG TUA P1 — GUSLINA

Wali kembar Zikra dan Zikri (16 tahun, tunagrahita) | 7 tahun dalam program

P1: Apakah ada perubahan pada kondisi fisik anak setelah mengikuti program?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — terlihat perkembangan fisik dan peningkatan kekuatan. Ada perkembangan fisik yang baik, peningkatan daya tahan — mereka jarang sakit — dan kekuatan fisik yang meningkat. Aktivitas yang padat membuat mereka tidur lebih cepat dan bangun dengan segar.

P2: Apakah mereka lebih mandiri setelah mengikuti olahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — setelah hari olahraga, mereka mencuci baju olahraga sendiri tanpa disuruh.

P3: Apakah Ibu mengetahui adaptasi yang diberikan dalam program?

[Tema: Kesadaran terhadap Adaptasi Program]

Guru-guru fokus dan berdedikasi. Anak-anak diberi kegiatan yang sesuai dengan tingkatannya.

ORANG TUA P2 — HERLINA DEWIFERI

Ibu Fajri (16 tahun, tunagrahita) | Atlet bulu tangkis

P1: Apakah ada perubahan pada kondisi fisik Fajri setelah mengikuti program?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — ia jarang sakit, meski sering keluar dalam panas atau hujan. Daya tahan fisiknya terbilang sangat kuat.

P2: Apakah olahraga membuatnya lebih mandiri?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya. Ketika tidak ada makanan di rumah, ia memasak mi sendiri. Ia mandiri dalam urusan sehari-hari.

ORANG TUA P3 — IKHSAN ENDRIZUL

Ayah siswa berusia 17 tahun (perenang/pelari)

P1: Apakah ada perubahan pada kondisi fisik putra Bapak?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — ada peningkatan yang cukup baik. Ia jarang sakit. Ia menjadi lebih mandiri.

ORANG TUA P4 — JUSNIWATI

Ibu siswa berusia 15–16 tahun (tunagrahita)

P1: Apakah ada perubahan pada kondisi fisik anak?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — secara fisik ia tampak lebih kuat. Ia kadang sakit, tapi tidak parah.

P2: Apakah Ibu mengetahui adaptasi yang diberikan dalam program?

[Tema: Kesadaran terhadap Adaptasi Program]

Saya kurang tahu detail sepenuhnya — saya sering bekerja ketika ia di rumah.

ORANG TUA P5 — ELI YARNI

Ibu Rio (15 tahun, tunagrahita) | 7 tahun dalam program

P1: Apakah ada perubahan kondisi fisik Rio setelah olahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — terlihat ia punya lebih banyak energi. Ia juga lebih sehat — jarang sakit sejak rutin berolahraga.

ORANG TUA P6 — MUNIARTI

Ibu Khalid (18 tahun) | Atlet renang

P1: Apakah ada perubahan pada kondisi fisik Khalid?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Daya tahan fisiknya meningkat — ia lebih tangguh. Ia sedikit lebih aktif di rumah.

ORANG TUA P7 — RENI SURYANI

Ibu Imam (remaja, tunagrahita) | Pemenang berbagai lomba

P1: Apakah ada perubahan kondisi fisik Imam sejak aktif berolahraga?

[Tema: Peningkatan Kemampuan Fisik yang Dapat Diamati]

Ya — daya tahan fisiknya meningkat sejak aktif berolahraga.